

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Shamsudinova M.U.

O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MA'NAVIY – MA'RIFIY ISHLARNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/SENTABR

